

Privacy-Preserving Real-Time Facial Expression Classification in the Browser

System Design and Tradeoff Evaluation (Technical Report)

Author: Michael Farrell Gunawan (GitHub: Nectarch) | Date: 31 Dec 2025

Live demo: <https://on-device-face-expression-demo-by-michael.vercel.app>

Repository: <https://github.com/Nectarch/on-device-face-expression-demo>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18109915>

Abstract

I built a browser-based webcam application that performs real-time face detection and facial expression classification entirely on-device (client-side). The system uses pre-trained face-api.js models (Tiny Face Detector and an expression classifier), renders bounding boxes and the top expression probabilities as a canvas overlay, and displays live performance metrics (render FPS and inference rate). I then evaluate responsiveness-robustness tradeoffs across (1) inference interval, (2) detector configuration (inputSize and scoreThreshold), and (3) output stabilization via exponential moving average (EMA) smoothing. On my device, results show rendering remains high-FPS while throughput is dominated by inference cost. Detector parameters strongly affect range and motion robustness, and EMA introduces a clear stability-latency tradeoff. Measurements also show sensitivity to illumination direction and pose, indicating that outputs are expression-category predictions rather than a ground-truth measure of internal emotional state.

1. Introduction

Modern browsers provide camera access, hardware-accelerated rendering, and sufficient local compute to run lightweight computer vision pipelines. This enables interactive demos without a server, improving privacy by keeping video frames on the user's device. This project presents an on-device browser demo for real-time facial expression classification and evaluates key tradeoffs affecting responsiveness and robustness.

Design goals

- Runs in Chrome/Edge without installing native software.
- Privacy-preserving: all inference runs locally with no video upload.
- Interactive: around 10 Hz inference is sufficient for real-time feedback.
- Reproducible and easy to evaluate (public link + source code).

2. System Overview

The application follows a standard real-time vision pipeline: model loading, webcam capture, periodic inference, and overlay rendering. A key design decision is to separate a high-frequency render loop from a throttled inference loop, allowing smooth UI while controlling compute cost.

2.1 Pipeline

- Load face-api.js model weights from /public/models.
- Request webcam frames via getUserMedia.
- Loop: run detection + expression inference at a throttled interval, smooth probabilities, render bounding boxes and top-k expressions, and update FPS/Hz metrics.

2.2 Privacy properties

All processing runs locally inside the browser. The only network access is for static assets (site files and model weights). The demo does not upload camera frames.

Figure 1 (System overview)

Figure 1: System UI overview showing on-device detection, top expression probabilities, and live performance metrics (FPS and inference rate).

3. Implementation

Frontend: React + TypeScript + Vite. Computer vision: face-api.js with Tiny Face Detector and an expression classifier. The overlay is drawn on a canvas aligned to the video element. The UI includes Start/Stop camera, theme toggle, Flip Camera (mirror), and a disclaimer about interpretation (at the bottom, cut off in these figures).

3.1 Real-time scheduling

I implement a render loop driven by `requestAnimationFrame` and throttle inference using a minimum time interval (default `inferEveryMs = 100 ms`). I also guard inference with a 'busy' flag so inference calls never overlap.

3.2 Baseline configuration

Unless otherwise stated, the default parameters are: `inferEveryMs = 100`, Tiny Face Detector `inputSize = 224`, `scoreThreshold = 0.4`, and EMA smoothing `Alpha = 0.25`.

3.3 Output stabilization

To reduce flicker, I apply exponential moving average (EMA) smoothing to expression probabilities. Smaller alpha values increase stability but add response delay. Larger values improve responsiveness but increase jitter as a tradeoff.

3.4 Overlay layout

To avoid covering the face, the label position is chosen relative to the face box and uses a sticky anchor strategy (keeping the previous side when it remains valid). When Flip Camera is enabled, I mirror the video for user familiarity and mirror drawing coordinates accordingly.

4. Evaluation Methodology

I evaluated the system on a Windows 11 laptop using Microsoft Edge browser. For each run, I started the camera, waited about 10 seconds for warm-up, then observed the on-screen metrics for approximately 30 seconds. I recorded render FPS and inference rate (Hz) shown by the app and noted qualitative robustness (distance, head motion, and lighting direction).

5. Results

5.1 Baseline performance

Baseline observed metrics: model load time 170–350 ms. Render FPS typically 119–120 (range 117–123). Inference rate typically about 10 Hz (range 8–11). Face detection was stable under normal conditions.

Metric	Observed (baseline)
Model load time	Typical 170–350 ms. Range 155–400 ms
Render FPS	Typical 119–120. Range 117–123
Inference rate (Hz)	Typical ~10. Range 8–11

5.2 Inference interval sweep

I varied `inferEveryMs` to measure responsiveness and saturation. At 200 ms, inference matched the target 5 Hz. At 50 ms, inference throughput saturated below the target (max about 18 Hz observed), with higher CPU usage. The baseline (100 ms) maintained approximately 10 Hz inference.

inferEveryMs	Observed inference (Hz)	Render FPS	Compute notes
200 ms	5	≈120 most of the time	CPU ≈3–7% (Task Manager)
100 ms (baseline)	Typical ~10 (range 8–11)	Typical 119–120 (range 117–123)	CPU ≈5–9% (Task Manager)
50 ms	Max ≈18 (did not reach 20)	Typical 119–120 (range 116–121)	CPU ≈7–11% (Task Manager)

5.3 Detector input size sweep

I varied Tiny Face Detector inputSize at the baseline inference interval (100 ms). Lower inputSize reduced operating distance. Higher inputSize improved distance and perceived detection success. Within these runs, render FPS and inference Hz remained stable, suggesting usability changes are driven by detector robustness rather than frame scheduling.

inputSize	Observed behavior (qualitative)	Notes
160	Detects reliably only at closer distance, but fails earlier at range	Low range. Stops detecting sooner
224 (baseline)	Detects at moderate range, noticeable box jitter in some conditions	Balanced default. Jitter visible at distance
320	Most accurate and farthest-reaching detection in tests	Best range in this evaluation

Figure 2 (Bounding box instability at distance)

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Theme: light

Start Camera Stop

Status
Running (on-device).
Privacy: All processing runs on your device. No video is uploaded.
Note: Display probabilities are calibrated to reduce neutral dominance.

Metrics
Model load: 323 ms
Render FPS: 120
Inference rate: 9 Hz

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Theme: light

Start Camera Stop

Status
Running (on-device).
Privacy: All processing runs on your device. No video is uploaded.
Note: Display probabilities are calibrated to reduce neutral dominance.

Metrics
Model load: 323 ms
Render FPS: 120
Inference rate: 10 Hz

Figure 2: InputSize comparison at the farthest stable distance. Top: 160. Bottom: 224 (beyond this distance, jitter increases and missed detections become more frequent).

Figure 3 (Far-range detection example)

Figure 3: Example of successful far-range face detection using Tiny Face Detector $inputSize = 320$

5.4 Detector score threshold sweep

I varied `scoreThreshold` (with `inputSize = 224`) to probe strictness vs robustness. Lower threshold improved robustness under head shaking. Higher threshold increased missed detections and reduced range. The baseline (0.4) is a balanced operating point under normal conditions.

scoreThreshold	Motion robustness	Range robustness
0.2	High (detected easily even when shaking)	Higher (relative)
0.4 (baseline)	Stable under normal use	Moderate (baseline)
0.6	Lower (harder to detect when shaking)	Lower (harder at distance)

5.5 EMA smoothing sweep

I varied `smoothingAlpha` to quantify stability–latency behavior. With `alpha = 0.10`, changes converged slowly (about 4 seconds to approach a new expression), consistent with exponential convergence. With `alpha = 0.50`, changes were near-instant (less than 1 second).

smoothingAlpha	Observed response behavior	Usability implication
0.10	Slow convergence (~4s). Slows near end of convergence	Very stable but slow change.
0.25 (baseline)	Balanced behavior (default)	Middle ground between responsiveness and stability
0.50	Very fast (<1s) response	Responsive and extremely quick, but jittery and unstable.

5.6 Illumination and pose sensitivity (qualitative)

Under stable lighting, UI theme (light vs dark) produced no meaningful changes beyond normal variance. However, changing illumination direction produced large distribution shifts: underlighting (from below) produced high “sad” ($\approx 80\%$) in my testing even with a neutral face, while overhead lighting produced a smaller shift and side lighting remained the most consistent. I also observed that head pose/orientation can shift predicted probabilities even with a neutral facial expression.

Figure 4 (Lighting direction sensitivity)

(a) Side lighting (left)

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Flip Camera

Theme: light

Start Camera Stop

neutral: 100%
sad: 0%
surprised: 0%

Status
Running (on-device).
Privacy: All processing runs on your device. No video is uploaded.
Note: Display probabilities are calibrated to reduce neutral dominance.

Metrics
Model load: 177 ms
Render FPS: 120
Inference rate: 10 Hz

(b) Underlighting (bottom)

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Flip Camera

Theme: light

Start Camera Stop

sad: 84%
angry: 11%
neutral: 4%

Status
Running (on-device).
Privacy: All processing runs on your device. No video is uploaded.
Note: Display probabilities are calibrated to reduce neutral dominance.

Metrics
Model load: 177 ms
Render FPS: 120
Inference rate: 9 Hz

(c) Overhead lighting

Figure 4: Lighting-direction sensitivity. (a) side lighting from the left (left/right behave similarly), (b) underlighting, which produces the largest shift in predicted probabilities, and (c) overhead lighting, which produces a smaller shift.

Figure 5 (Pose/orientation sensitivity)

(a) Tilt right

(b) Tilt left

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Theme: light

Start Camera Stop

Status

Running (on-device).

Privacy: All processing runs on your device. No video is uploaded.

Note: Display probabilities are calibrated to reduce neutral dominance.

Metrics

Model load: 323 ms

Render FPS: 120

Inference rate: 5 Hz

(c) Tilt down

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Theme: light

Start Camera Stop

Status

Running (on-device).

Privacy: All processing runs on your device. No video is uploaded.

Note: Display probabilities are calibrated to reduce neutral dominance.

Metrics

Model load: 323 ms

Render FPS: 120

Inference rate: 5 Hz

(d) Tilt up

On-device Facial Expression (Webcam)

Figure 5: Pose sensitivity under a neutral face, predicted probabilities shift with head orientation: (a) tilt right (*sad*-dominant), (b) tilt left (*happy* increases), (c) tilt down (*neutral*-dominant), and (d) tilt up (*neutral* decreases with higher *angry/happy*).

6. Discussion

Rendering remained smooth across tested configurations, while inference rate saturated as the target interval became aggressive. This indicates the application is inference-bound rather than render-bound. Detector configuration (inputSize and scoreThreshold) strongly affected robustness (range and motion tolerance), and EMA smoothing provided a tunable stability–latency tradeoff.

6.1 Practical defaults

For a public demo aiming for interactive feedback with minimal CPU load, the default settings (inferEveryMs = 100, inputSize = 224, scoreThreshold = 0.4, smoothingAlpha = 0.25) provided a balanced operating point. If detection under motion is prioritized, lowering scoreThreshold toward 0.2 improved robustness in my tests. If range is prioritized, increasing inputSize toward 320 improved detection at distance in my tests.

7. Limitations and Ethical Considerations

- Expression categories are not internal emotion. The model outputs label probabilities based on pixels. It is not a measurement of emotional state.
- Environmental sensitivity. Lighting direction and head pose can shift predictions without a change in affect.
- No ground-truth accuracy evaluation. This report focuses on real-time performance and robustness, not classification accuracy against labeled datasets.

8. Reproducibility

To reproduce: install Node.js (18+ recommended), install dependencies, and run the development server. Model files must be present in public/models. A public live demo is provided.

Commands:

```
npm install  
npm run dev
```

```
npm run build  
npm run preview
```

References

- [1] face-api.js repository (pre-trained models and API):
<https://github.com/justadudewhohacks/face-api.js>
- [2] MDN getUserMedia documentation:
<https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/MediaDevices/getUserMedia>
- [3] Vite documentation:
<https://vite.dev/>
- [4] React documentation:
<https://react.dev/>